

Early detection of Leaf blight, Black rot and Esca in Mature Grapevines (LBED)

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Abstract

Leaf blight, Black rot, and Esca are three different major plant diseases detected in mature grape vines. These three diseases look extremely similar to each other morphologically but are caused by different phytopathogenic fungi. The objective of this research is to develop a practical and efficient solution that can accurately distinguish between the diseases, Leaf blight (caused by *Phomopsis viticola*), Black rot (caused by *Guignardia bidwellii*), and Esca (caused by *Phaeoconiella chlamydospore*, *Phaeoacremonium spp.*, and *Fomitiporia mediterranea*) in grapevines. In order to make disease identification simple and quick, an analysis of leaf morphology is conducted. To analyse the leaves, a deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was developed. The CNN analyses an image of a leaf, correlates its characteristics, and diagnoses which of the three diseases has affected the plant within 10 seconds. The CNN is made up of ten layers, the CNN has a database consisting of 11,711 images divided into four classes, CNN was developed using TensorFlow-Keras in Python, integrated using Hugging Face, and has a 98.19% accuracy.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Networks, Leaf blight, Black rot, Esca

1. Introduction

1.1 Project statement

The Leaf Blight, Black Rot, and Esca Detection (LBED) System employ image analysis to classify and diagnose grapevine diseases. One significant challenge in this task is the visual similarity among the three diseases, as one of the key symptoms in all three diseases is irregular brown lesions on grapevine leaves. In spite of their similar appearances, these lesions result from different pathogens. In spite of this challenge, our model can distinguish between all 3 with ease.

(Image1: Black Rot, Esca, Leaf Blight and a Healthy leaf.)

1.2 Research Objective:

The objective of this research is to develop a practical and efficient solution that can accurately distinguish between Grapevine Leaf Blight (caused by *Guignardia bidwellii*), Black Rot (caused by *Phomopsis viticola*), and Esca (caused by *Phaeoacremonium spp.*, and *Fomitiporia mediterranea*) in grapevines. The focus is on the analysis of leaf morphology to facilitate easy and rapid disease identification. This research aims to achieve high accuracy and speed of disease differentiation, resulting in improved grapevine health and yield.

1.3 What are Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and how are we utilizing it?

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm that extrapolates pixel-level data from images. This study analyzes individual pixels in images of leaves from affected grape vines using a CNN framework. CNNs can identify the key features in an image as well as classify the information extracted from the image, allowing the model to isolate which features are important in diagnosing the three. CNNs are gaining popularity for identification of diseases both in animals and plants.

1.4 Past work

This research was inspired by the works of outside researchers working to develop CNNs for classification and detection of Leaf Blight, Black rot and Esca in grape vines. For example, The research by Jiajun Zhu, Man Cheng, Qifan Wang, Hongbo Yuan, and Zhenjiang Cai of the College of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering, Hebei Agricultural University, Baoding, China. Developed a model that had an average accuracy of $\approx 93.43\%$ ¹.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data Gathering

The data used to train the model was sourced from the dataset provided by the researchers mentioned from the Hebei Agricultural University, Baoding, China¹. Furthermore, dataset was also obtained from sites like Kaggle².

2.2 Model Structure

The **Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)** developed to effectively distinguish between the three diseases (Leaf blight, Black rot, and Esca) using images of leaf part of the plant.

The CNN developed has a total of 10 layers. Which consists of **4 Convolutional Layers, 2 MaxPooling layers, 1 Flatten Layer, 2 Dense layers** and an **Input/Output layer**.

Before feeding the images to our model, Firstly, the images are sorted into 4 different classes- "Esca", "Black Rot", "Leaf Blight" and "Healthy". Then the images are reshaped into the size **100px*100px**(height*width), '100px' was chosen as it was the standard size for most of the images in

the dataset. Then the data was normalized by dividing all the values in the numerical array by 255.0 in order to scale all the data points into the range [0-1]. We then performed one hot encoding on our target variables to create label vectors that were representative of the categorization amongst the four classes (“Esca”, “Black Rot”, “Leaf Blight” and “Healthy”). The Deep Convolutional Neural Network used in this study was formulated with the help of Keras/TensorFlow Python library.

The neural network is a standard sequential base model containing 4 Convolutional Layers with **Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU)** activation function, 2 MaxPooling layers, 1 Flatten Layer, and 2 Dense layers. Image 2 shows the positioning of the layers. After all the convolutional layers, 2 dense layers were formulated, first one with 128 neurons with ReLU activation and second dense layer with 4 neurons and softmax activation.

Compiling the model, we used an **Adam optimizer** with a learning rate of **0.001**, as well as Sparse **Categorical-Crossentropy** loss functions. Furthermore, we ran our data for a total of **10 epochs**. A hyperparameter tuning technique was used to refine the network structure by adjusting activation functions, epochs, neurons, optimizers, and learning rates. Approximately **9%** of the model's performance was improved by hyperparameter tuning.

(Image2: LBED CNN)

2.3 Important Metrics

Following is some of the most important metrics for a CNN model.

2.3.1 Accuracy

Accuracy (1) is an extremely important metric in multi-class classification. To compute accuracy, we take the sum of the True Positive and True Negative results from our model and divide that by all of the entries. True Positives and True Negatives are the elements that are correctly classified by the model.

$$(1) \quad Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad 2.3.2$$

Macro F1 Score

To compute Macro F1-Score (5), we first computed the Macro-Precision (3) and Macro-Recall (4) scores. Macro-Precision is computed by taking the average precision (1) for each predicted class and Macro-Recall is similarly computed by taking the average recall (2) for each predicted class. The Macro approach considers all the classes as equal, meaning that each class has the same weight in the computed score - there is no distinction between classes that have more entities and classes that have fewer entities

$$(1) \quad Precision_k = \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k}$$

$$(2) \quad Recall_k = \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FN_k}$$

$$(3) \quad MacroAveragePrecision = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K Precision_k}{K}$$

$$(4) \quad MacroAverageRecall = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K Recall_k}{K}$$

$$(5) \quad Macro \text{ F1-Score} = 2 * \left(\frac{MacroAveragePrecision * MacroAverageRecall}{MacroAveragePrecision^{-1} + MacroAverageRecall^{-1}} \right)$$

3. Results

3.1 Model Performance

LBED system achieved an accuracy of 98.19%.

LBED system also achieved a max F1 Score of 0.99 models.

3.2 Important graphs regarding the model

Figure 1 LBED Confusion Matrix

Figure 2 ROC Curve of LBED

Figure 3 Train Loss Vs Validation Loss graph of LBED

Figure 4 Train Accuracy Vs Validation Accuracy of LBED

3.3 Outcome

The LBED System was able to efficiently and accurately classify all four different classes in a timely manner. Moreover, the model exceeded expectations and outperformed other models in terms of performance. As part of our long-term plan, we intend to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the LBED system in the near future.

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